

EXPLORATION OF CONCEPTS THROUGH A COGNITIVE-STYLISTIC LENS

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Modern cognitive linguistics actively applies interpretive strategies that take into account not only the characteristics of a particular utterance and the general body of knowledge, but also pay special attention to the personal aspects of the interpreter and his/her subjective perception of the text in his/her own mental space. Justification allows for a deeper and more complete understanding of the processes of text interpretation and perception, taking into account the individual characteristics of each reader or researcher.

The approach is justified because in real life the uniqueness of the author's and reader's personalities precludes a complete coincidence of their semantic perceptions. The author's freedom in choosing interpretative solutions, individual approaches to text enrichment and differences in the linguistic, cultural upbringing and ethical experience of the reader may differ significantly. For this purpose, modern linguistics applies cognitive-discursive analysis in the analysis of the artistic text, which is not limited to the consideration of the text only from linguistic positions, but in addition, takes into account extra-linguistic factors.

The problem of studying the interpretation of knowledge about the world is often associated with many factors and complexities. A key aspect that arises when investigating this problem is the subjectivity of interpretation since, people have different background knowledge, cultural contexts and personal experiences that influence how they interpret information about the world. This subjectivity can create diversity in the ways in which different people perceive and understand facts. And also the limitations of language, as language, as a means of communicating knowledge, is sometimes limited in its ability to accurately and completely describe complex phenomena and concepts. This can cause distortions in the transmission of information and its subsequent interpretation. The influence of bias and stereotyping is justified, as people can be subject to bias and stereotypes that affect their ability to interpret information objectively, leading to distorted perceptions of events and phenomena in the world. There are also cognitive distortions, such as

confirmation of existing beliefs, that affect the way people interpret new information, which can make it difficult to perceive facts objectively.

The dynamic nature of knowledge also plays a special role, due to the fact that knowledge about the world is constantly changing and evolving, which creates a challenge in tracking changes in knowledge interpretation over time and in adapting to new data. Finally, communication barriers, where lack of clarity in the expression of information, misunderstandings between cultures or language groups create obstacles to the correct interpretation of knowledge.

To better understand the problem of interpreting knowledge about the world, research must take these aspects into account and take into account the socio-cultural and individual contexts that shape and perceive knowledge.

The linguistic elements are aimed at realising the overall communicative-creative strategy. For the interpreter-linguist, language and its components serve as the "instrumental" basis of artistic communication, ensuring the synergy of all aspects of the form and content of the text. The action of language in this context exceeds the impact of each individual element on the semantic integrity of the literary work. The study of a fiction text using the cognitive-discursive method is one of the main trends in literary studies, which combines the analysis of cognitive and discursive aspects, allowing us to consider texts taking into account their content, structure and contextual relationships.

The study of the cognitive aspect focuses on analysing the processes of perception, interpretation and creative re-creation of artistic texts. This approach highlights the role of the reader in the formation of meaning from the text, his/her ability to organise information, form images and construct representations.

The cognitive-discursive method facilitates the discovery of deep meanings and ideas embedded in artistic texts and the analysis of their aesthetic value. The method supports literary scholars and critics, stimulating the development of new research methods and the formation of a more complete perception of artistic works.

The study within cognitive linguistics focuses not only on linguistic abilities, but rather on their use and how language develops in the process of a person's personal formation. The field of cognitive linguistics is vast and closely interconnected with scientific disciplines such as sociolinguistics, psycholinguistics, and ethnolinguistics.

In conclusion, it is important to note that when using cognitive analysis to analyse artistic discourse, attention is paid to comprehension and

interpretation, which is a cognitive procedure aimed at identifying the semantic content of the text. Consequently, discourse comprehension and interpretation is a complex cognitive process involving the processing of textual information. Of particular importance in this process are the conceptualisation and categorisation of various knowledge structures underlying artistic discourse.

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